

WORK FAMILY CONFLICT AND ACADEMIC JOB STRESS ON LIFE SATISFACTION OF PRIVATE UNIVERSITY LECTURERS IN OGUN STATE, NIGERIA

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11199720>

Abstract

Work-Family Conflict and Academic Job stress can influence Life satisfaction thereby affecting optimal production of Lecturers. The study investigates the impact of work-family conflict and academic job stress on life satisfaction among private university lecturers and the role of marital status and work family conflict on life satisfaction. Cross-sectional survey design was used and randomly (head/ tail) selected alphabetically six private universities in Ogun state. The questionnaire consisted Life satisfaction scale, Work-Family Conflict scale and newly developed scale on Academics' job stress. 120 university lecturers was targeted and analysed with 2x2ANOVA and linear regression. Findings revealed that work-family conflict and academic job stress significantly influence life satisfaction of university lecturers, there was a significant interaction effect between marital status and work-family conflict on life satisfaction among university lecturers. This study recommends that university management should develop strategies to reduce lecturers' dissatisfaction, and employ more hands-on deck to reduce workload.

Keywords: Work-Family Conflict, Academics Stress, Life Satisfaction, Lecturer

1 INTRODUCTION

Work-family conflict and academic stress can both have significant impacts on an individual's life satisfaction and production. Work-family conflict occurs when the demands and responsibilities of work interfere with family or personal life, or when family demands interfere with work commitments. This conflict can manifest in different ways, such as long working hours, high job demands, inflexible work schedules, or difficulties in balancing work and family roles.

Work-family conflict can lead to reduced life satisfaction. It can be in form of strain and stress (Joseph, Thomas, Antonio et al., 2017). Balancing work and family responsibilities can be challenging and stressful. Constantly juggling multiple roles can lead to emotional exhaustion, fatigue, and burnout, which can decrease overall life satisfaction. It can also lead to guilt and dissatisfaction, when individuals feel torn between work and family obligations, they may experience guilt or dissatisfaction in both domains. This dissatisfaction can spill over into other areas of life, impacting overall life satisfaction. And lastly it can cause relationship strain, work-family conflict can strain relationships with family members, partners, and friends. Conflict arising from unmet family expectations or neglected personal relationships can negatively affect well-being and life satisfaction.

Work-family conflict hurts lecturers in the Universities, Work-family conflict reduces lecturers' productivity and job performance of Universities lecturers. It also affects lecturer turnover, psychological distress, and life satisfaction (Greenhaus and Beutell, 2015) In other respects, excellent compatibility between family and work gives a sense of high achievement in the workplace since it motivates individuals (Byrne, 2010).

A saying according to Dewhurst and Fitzpatrick, 2022 that "a happy employee is a more productive employee" Likewise, a happy lecturer is a more productive lecturer. Meaning if the family life of a lecturer is balanced her /his work life would also be balanced and he would be more effective at work. Academic stress has negative effects on the physical and mental health of University lecturers, some literature have shown that most academics nurture health problems more than other professionals, such health problems like high blood pressure, stroke, and mental health issues like insomnia, anxiety and depression which affects the long-term relationship and psychological contract between universities and the lecturers (Hall and Mirvis 2016: Edisson 2015)

Academic stress among lecturers is a major contributing factor to many psychological illnesses which also plague today's society (Ferguson and Bourgeault, 2022). It has become a frequent problem across the occupations as many academic institutions nowadays demand a lot from their university lecturers to outrun their competitors. Conversely, Family Work conflict arises especially for married ones who have marital obligations to their spouse and children. Family responsibilities impede work activities, such as having to cancel an important meeting because a child suddenly took ill (Frone et al., 2022).

1.1 Statement of the problem

It has been found that certain health challenges like dementia, insomnia, stroke, hypertension and depression leading to death are common among teachers and lecturers (Gahagan 2018; Correntte, Ferguson and Bourgeault, 2022). This is due to the high demand of their work which has caused negligence on their health, thereby they deteriorate in physical and mental health due to stress and their sedentary lifestyle with their books. A majour sign of stress among lecturers is the greyish or white hair that most of them in the profession have as they progress in the career which is due to stress (Rosensberg, Rausser, Ren et al., 2021). Some authors like Kinnunen, Vermulst, and Mäkikangas (2020) have also recognized the importance of the relationship between Work-Family Conflict and health as factors to be considered in well-being. Stress is a problem that cannot be overlooked. Stress has negative effect on individual's productivity at work place. Consequently, stress affects individual, his or her family, the community, and the nation at large.

The experience of stress is not peculiar to lectures alone, but career individuals are also affected. Lecturer's huge work demands such as teaching, writing, publication, attending conferences, mentoring, attending internal and external meetings, meeting up with deadlines and doing administrative works, just to mention a few. Especially in private universities where employees maximize human resources and make an individual do a ten-man job, unlike in public universities. Bearing in mind that these lectures also have families and have expectations and roles as father, mother, husband, wife, child, sister, brother, aunt or uncle, on one hand, and employees on another. The home-work interface stress, therefore, seems to particularly affect adversely (Son Hing, Sakr, Srenson, et al, 2023)). Their role at home seems to be affected by their work likewise their work seems to be affected due to divided attention from home or from work. This could in turn have an adverse effect on their health, wellbeing and life satisfaction.

A major gap in study is that, most research on Academic Job stress has been among primary and secondary school teachers while there has been little or no particular study linking Work family conflict and academic stress among university lecturers. It is for these aforementioned reasons that this study seeks to expand the range of possible variables in the relationship between Work-Family conflict, Lecturer's academic Job stress and life satisfaction among Private University lecturers.

The specific objective are as follows,

1. To determine the impact of Work-Family conflict on Life Satisfaction among private universities lecturers
2. To examine the influence of Academic Job stress on Life satisfaction among private university lecturers
3. To examine the roles of marital status and work family conflict on life satisfaction.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

Researcher Jussi Suikkanen's theory of life satisfaction is an intriguing one: a person is satisfied with her life when "a more informed and rational hypothetical version of her" would judge that her life fulfills her ideal life-plan (Suikkanen's, 2011). This theory avoids one of the main issues that plagues the simpler version of this theory—that a person is happy when she judges that her life fulfills her ideal life-plan.

The main contributing factors to life satisfaction are not completely understood yet, and the weight they are given by each individual varies; but, research has found that they likely fall into one of four sequential categories: Life chances, Course of events, Flow of experience and Evaluation of life (Veenhoven, 1996). But for this study it is been measured as evaluation of life.

2.1 Role conflict theory (1985)

It was developed by Greenhaus and Beutell (1985). When an individual's roles in one domain (job) clash with the other (family), conflict is believed to occur, according to role conflict theory. Conflict has three aspects, according to Greenhaus and Beutell (1985). The first is a conflict based on time, which occurs when one position necessitates more time and leaves less time for the other role's involvement. As a result, the amount of time spent at home is determined by marital status, family size, children and dependent parents, and a lack of social support, whereas the amount of time spent at work is impacted by the amount of time spent commuting.

Another kind of conflict is strain-based conflict, which happens when a person's stress or exhaustion from one function impacts the work of another. Finally, the conflict arises when the performance of the two domains are incompatible, for example, expressing one's emotions, being emotional, and being sensitive in the job. A person's cognitive judgment of his or her life's conditions is known as "life satisfaction," and studies argue that the two domains of work and family have an influence on this subjective measure. Since life satisfaction covers a wide range of activities of daily routine, conflict in work and non-work domains disrupt emotions. There is a link between role conflict at work and in the home, and poorer levels of job and life satisfaction, according to Greenhaus and Beutell (1985).

3 METHODOLOGY

A cross sectional method was used to select samples for this study. The researcher drew the sample from all 13 private universities in Ogun state as at 2021, the universities were arranged in alphabetic order and randomly selected 6 universities using head or tail technique. A total of 120 university lecturers was expected at least 20 from each university, but 73% response was gotten making. The questionnaire consisted of scales measuring life satisfaction by Diener 1985, Work and family conflict by Haslam, D. *et. al.*, 2015 and 18 item scale measuring Academic Job stress developed by the researcher, its cronbach alpha is 0.85. The data was analysed with 2X2 ANOVA and linear regression analysis for the statistics.

4 ANALYSIS

The first hypothesis stated that, there would be a significant influence of work-family conflict on life satisfaction among university lecturers in Ogun State. Linear regression analysis was used to test the hypothesis. The results indicate that, there was significant influence of work family conflict on life

satisfaction, $R^2 = .111$, $F(1,86) = 10.727$, $p < .05$. The result also indicates that 11% variance of life satisfaction among university lecturer is accounted for by work family conflict. This hypothesis was supported.

The second hypothesis stated that there would be a significant influence of academic job stress on life satisfaction among university lecturers in Ogun State. Linear regression analysis was used to test the hypothesis. The result indicate that, there was significant influence of Academic Job stress on Life satisfaction, $R^2 = .112$, $F(1,86) = 10.874$, $p < .01$. The result also indicates that 11% variance of life satisfaction among university lecturers is accounted for by academic stress. The hypothesis was supported. Hypothesis three stated that, married university lecturers will significantly have higher work family conflict on life satisfaction than single university lecturers was analyzed with 2X2 ANOVA. The result shows that there was significant interaction effect between marital status and work family conflict on life satisfaction among university lecturers, $F(1,84) = 10.261$, $P < .05$. Also, work family conflict has significant main effect on life satisfaction, $F(1,84) = 5.583$, $p < .05$. However, marital status has no significant main effect on life satisfaction, $F(1,84) = .749$, $p > .05$. Hypothesis was supported.

It further explained the mean interaction between marital status and work-family conflict which shows that married university lecturers with low work family conflict scored high on life satisfaction ($\bar{x} = 17.48$) than single university lecturers with low work family conflict scored high on life satisfaction ($\bar{x} = 14.42$), married university lecturers with high work family conflict scored lower ($\bar{x} = 13.29$) on Life satisfaction than single university lecturers with low work family conflict ($\bar{x} = 15.05$).

5 DISCUSSION

Impact of Work-Family conflict on Life satisfaction

Based on the findings of this research, it is shown that there is a significant influence of work family conflict on life satisfaction. This is supported by Nicole (2013) that work-family conflict has been linked to an increase in chronic weariness, increased absenteeism from the workplace, poor physical health, and even the breakdown of families (Joseph et al., 2017). This means that the work-family conflict is a factor that affects life satisfaction of private university lecturers.

Influence of Academic Job stress on Life satisfaction

Our findings found that there is a significant influence of academic job stress on life satisfaction. This also means that academic job stress can also affect the life satisfaction of lectures in private universities. This means that the work load that could be eustress can have a negative tone on the life satisfaction and effective production (Eddison, 2015) of lecturers in private universities. Ferguson and Bourgeault 2022 also supports that teachers' stress level is as a result of work load and lack of resources which affect their home lives and productivity is being affected.

Influence of married university lecturers and Work-family conflict on Life satisfaction.

The result of our findings shows that, there was not really a difference in the level of Work-Family conflict in terms of marital status on Life satisfaction. The finding shows that the married university lecturers that have higher level of work-family conflict were low on life satisfaction compared to single university lecturers. This is also supported by Mart, Hanum and Holipah, (2023) that married women have low turnover intentions on their work than the Single which is as a result of the work-family conflict.

6 CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATIONS

This study concludes that Work family conflict and Academic Job stress significantly influenced Life satisfaction of Private university lecturers which will in turn affect their productivity. Issues that built up Academic job stress were work load, lack of co-operation with colleagues, not being appreciated on the job

by the university management, low salary, lack of autonomy and lack of promotion. If these issues are considered academic job stress could be reduced. It was also concluded that married private university lecturers who were high work family conflict were low on life satisfaction, thereby affecting optimum production. University management should set up work-life policies and programs that would allow lecturers bring their families to hang out in gatherings together with colleagues. This would support their university lecturers in fulfilling both their official duties at the workplace and their individual responsibilities outside the workplace as well. It will also make spouses and children understand the work schedule of the lecturer.

7 LIMITATIONS AND FURTHER STUDIES

This study is limited in sample size. Further research should get larger samples for generalizability. It is also suggested that future research should investigate the years of marriage and Work cadre of Work-family conflict on Life satisfaction.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I acknowledge the SRW committee of Chrisland University ably led by Professor. T.O Akinbobola for funding us to attend this Conference.

AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

Author Contributions: Conceptualization O.A Oyinlola, Economic Concepts O.A Adeyemi Literature review E.T Adeduro, Methodology O.A Oyinlola and E.T Adeduro, Writing and Editing O.A Oyinlola, E.T Adeduro and O.J Adeyemi

All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: Not Applicable

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: The data utilized for this study will be made available upon reasonable request.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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